

**FROM THE DARK ROOM TO LIBERTY:
A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF R.K. NARAYAN'S "THE DARK
ROOM" NOVEL AND VOLGA'S TELUGU NOVEL "SWETCHA"**

Dr. T. Ashok
Associate Professor
Andhra University Campus
Kakinada, A.P

Noojilla Srinivas
Lecturer in English
Govt. College (A)
Rajahmundry, A.P

Y. Pani Rao
Senior Lecturer in English
Govt. Polytechnic College
Nellore A.P

Feminist writings in India:

Feminism mainly started in Europe, as a campaign for the rights of women, including social, political, and economic equality with men. Between 17th-19th centuries, these campaigners fought for women's right to own property, to have access to higher education, and to vote. Latter, the campaign spread to the other parts of the world. In 20th century, the campaign's emphasis shifted to the goals of equal social, economic and employment opportunities for women.

In India, some writers in the pre-independence era tried to touch the problems of women in their works of literature. But in these works, feminism was handled under restricted circumstances only. With the advancement of time, however, feminism has been accepted in India, setting aside the patriarchal pre-domination to certain extent. The feminist writers include not only female writers, but also male writers who are sympathizers of women.

R.K. Narayan - "The Dark Room":

R.K. Narayan (1907-2001) is well known for his fiction, especially his novels, which represent the microcosmic India of his

times. His novels serve as socio-historical chronicles of both Pre- and Post- Independent India. His stories are mainly set in the fictional town of Malgudi. His characters are realistic portrayals from life. It is interesting to see his books from the feministic perspective as no one seriously agrees with this statement and Narayan himself did never claim so. Particularly one novel of Narayan "The Dark Room" shows the writer on the side of women.

"The Dark Room" is the story of Savitri, a middle class housewife, whose husband is an employee in an insurance company. Her husband, Ramani is a dominant, excessively critical and self-centered person. They have three children. The first scene sees him criticising everything that his wife serves him on the table. He curses the cook and freely taunts his wife. At work, he enters into an affair with a woman called Shanta Bai.

Unable to bear the humiliation and neglect, Savitri confronts her husband who dismisses her objections. Desolate at being taken so entirely for granted she raises her voice and then is determined to leave the house. She wants to take the kids along, but Ramani stops her harshly. "Don't touch them or talk to them. Go yourself, if you want. They are my children," he shouts.

Depressed in heart, Savitri wanders alone in the street and even plunges herself into the river. But overcome by fear, she shouts out for help. A blacksmith by day and burglar by night saves her. He brings along his wife, Ponni who tries to befriend Savitri. She offers her shelter and food. But Savitri refuses to eat anything not earned by her. She is disgusted at being at the mercy of the men in her life – father, brother, husband. She doesn't want to take any one's charity. She starts working at a temple as a cleaner. But in a day she realises the impracticality of her choice and returns home. Ramani is relieved to find her back, less for her sake, and more to keep up social pretenses.

Narayan quite clearly feels a deep anguish at the wife being treated shabbily and leaves no opportunity to portray the ugliness and selfishness of the husband's character. Narayan's sympathies are with Savitri though he resists from making a grand feminist statement. She leaves the house for valid reasons, but reconciles and comes back. Narayan was a realist and understood the limitations of people in their context and worlds. Narayan is effective in his portrayal of Ramani, a vain, sarcastic, self-serving man. Also, the part where Savitri leaves and encounters a different world is poignant.

Olga's Telugu Novel – Swetcha:

The Telugu novel 'Swetcha' was written by P. Lalitha Kumari, who is well-known by her pen name 'Olga', and published in 1987. This novel appears like a manifesto of Feminist writers in Andhra Pradesh. Unlike R.K. Narayan, Olga wrote this novel with a specific purpose of propagating the philosophy of feminism through literature.

The protagonist in the novel 'Aruna' writes her final M.A. exams. Because of her middle class family, she grows under control, right from her childhood. After she attains age, her father and brother start setting limitations to her freedom. For this, to some extent, her maternal aunt Kanakamma is also responsible. She lost her husband at very young age and came to her younger brother's house with some wealth. As she could not enjoy her marital life properly she always expresses her jealous and sadistic nature by wielding command over her sister-in-law and niece Aruna. Because of the love for her wealth, nobody dares talking against her. Particularly, she tries to suppress Aruna always. She thinks of getting Aruna married at the age of 15 years as was done in Aruna's elder sister's case. She always makes fuss over the issue of Aruna's marriage. Aruna opposes this suppression and limitations right from her childhood in her heart.

In such a family, if Aruna could pursue her studies up to Post Graduation, it was only due to the inability of her father in finding money for her marriage. Otherwise, he would have married her off long back and reduced his burden.

Aruna thinks of marrying her classmate Prakasam whom she loves and wants to join in a job for financial freedom. Immediately after getting a job, she marries Prakasam. Though Aruna is not willing to beget children immediately, Prakasam makes her oblige with his adamant nature and male chauvinism. Right from the beginning, Prakasam did not like Aruna doing job, and taking financial decisions herself. Though Aruna balances both the family and office affairs effectively, Prakasam always troubles her with his words. His anger over her increases when he finds Aruna participating in strike in her college for full salary, working for a progressive magazine 'Abhyudaya', moving among people for the magazine, interviewing the prostitute women at Mehendi area, etc. His opinion is that his wife should limit herself for the household responsibilities only. He asks her not to involve in the problems of the society. Finally he threatens her by asking her to choose between family and social service.

Aruna slowly understands that all the women around her also suffer from similar problems. She could not bear the fact that her colleague Kesava Rao, who appears like a progressive person and talks about social reforms, also confines his wife to the kitchen at home. Once she understands the nature of bondages, she also understands the form of 'liberty'. Finally she decides to come out of the bondages of the family. Leaving her family, she thinks of helping the society and fellow needy women to the extent possible.

Comparison between the two Novels: Though they belong to different times and genres, "The Dark Room" and "Swetcha" novels reflect some common problems faced by women. They are:

1. Family and Gender Roles:

The main focus of the two writers is the slow erosion of a woman's individual identity within a family. Both of them attacked on the myth of the 'ideal' family by showing how the family is a space where gender roles are often decided by the men of the house. In Narayan's novel, the protagonist is symbolically named 'Savitri' after one of the most revered models of Indian womanhood. She does all that is expected of her, and serves the family with utmost diligence. Despite this, she has no role to play in decision-making. The cook is unhappy but she cannot feed him. The child is ill but she cannot tell him to stay at home. Similar situation is faced by Aruna in Swetcha novel. She does not have a right on issues like when she wants to be a mother, etc. In these two novels, the criticism of the family system focuses on the following:

- The woman does not choose her roles – the roles are given to her, as mother, wife, etc.
- The absence of any role for women in decision-making.
- The complete erasure of her identity and personality due to the pressure of the roles assigned to her.

In the scene where Savitri leaves the house she says:

"...I don't possess anything in this world. What possession can a woman call her own except her body? Everything else that she has is her father's her husband's or her son's...."

What Savitri is saying is that her entire identity comes from somebody else- her husband, father or son. She owns nothing, even her identity is not her own. Interestingly, though Aruna in Swetcha novel is a Post Graduate and an employee, she too faces the similar problem of identity as a daughter before marriage and as a wife after marriage.

'The Dark Room' and 'Swetcha' novels show how gender roles are instilled in the children from a very early age. The father in Narayan's novel seeks to allot behavior, recreation and attitude to the children so that they fit the gender roles for adult life. Thus boys will not play with dolls becomes a kind of rule. Similarly, in Swetcha novel, Aruna experiences a different treatment compared to her brother in making her choices related to studies, etc. and faces criticism from her father and aunt. This is a form of 'socialization' where boys and girls are fitted, trained to fill certain gendered roles, even if they are unwilling to do so.

Society's pre-determined roles for girls and boys are played out within the family. The social roles for gender are first developed as forms of behaviour within the family. The family, in other words, reproduces the gender roles.

These two novels make a strong criticism of this condition where:

- The family is seen as a fundamental unit for individual identity;
- The family functions in such a way that the man can choose his identity but the woman is not given this choice;
- The family indoctrinates the children in gender roles so that they fit into such roles for the society;

2. Individualism and the woman:

In both the novels 'The Dark Room' and 'Swetcha' the issue of woman's individualism is dealt with strongly.

In a fiery speech Savitri, tells Ramani:

"I am a human being... You men will never grant us that. For you we are playthings when you feel like hugging and slaves at other times."

In the novel *Swetcha* also, Aruna tells her friend about her husband Prakasam that ‘...he loves her if she behaves according to his wishes, otherwise, he becomes serious...’. In another situation, she doubts whether her husband loves her as an individual or just because she is beautiful and intelligent. Thus, these situations are comments on individualism – for human to respect another as a human. They are pointing two things:

- The reduction of women to commodities.
- The absence of an individual identity except as somebody’s property, slave or thing.

Savitri comes to enjoy her identity when she starts working in the temple on her own and earns her food. She feels a great thrill when she lights the oven and cooks a little rice for herself. She says: “This is my own rice, my very own, and I am not obliged to anyone for this. This is nobody’s charity to me.”

There is an interesting play of space that Narayan engages in, which reflects his theme of individualism. Whenever Savitri is upset and humiliated she retires to the ‘dark room’ in her house. Interestingly when she goes to live in the temple, she again gets a ‘dark room’. The ‘dark room’ is therefore the only space where Savitri is truly conscious of herself. In her house it becomes the space where she is truly her individual self. It shuts her off from her tyrannical husband, her dependent family and her pre-determined gender roles.

Aruna in *Swetcha* novel tries to assert her individuality right from the beginning. Interestingly, her individuality is not just for her sake, but for the sake of society, because she wants to work for the welfare of poor girls and unfortunate prostitutes of Mehendi area.

In addition to the above mentioned common points, ‘*Swetcha*’ novel focuses on several problems that today’s woman face, the way their

lives are being reined by the men around her, be it in her family or her work space.

- It deals with the issues like:
 - restricting the freedom of girl child;
 - husband dictating terms to wife and opposing her;
 - woman lacking freedom to decide when to have children;
 - rape in married life; and
 - laws that decide that children stay with their father when husband and wife are divorced;
- It also supports the idea of freedom to the adults, to have live-in relationship without entering matrimony, by creating the character of 'Uma', Aruna's friend.
- In Olga's own words, "This novel questions the system which always tries to hold back women in families, politics or movements and suggests that matters which commonly occur in middle class families need to be recognized as social issues and treated as such."

The major difference between the two protagonists 'Savitri' and 'Aruna' is that while Savitri leaves the house, but returns home after few days, after experiencing brief span of individuality. Aruna, right from the beginning fights for her individuality and leaves the house, almost with a clear determination of not returning to the marital life, as she wishes to serve the fellow women in the society. Aruna's character keeps on evolving throughout the story and attains her desired goal, her individuality, and her freedom.

In the words of Olga:

"This liberty is not something given by others. Not achieved from anybody. Liberty is recognizing the important things necessary for our

needs and identity. It is liberty for us from ourselves. It is liberty from the thoughts, opinions and customs that have been habituated for us right from our birth. It is the liberty from the beliefs that have been ingrained in us.”

Conclusion:

As seen from the two novels, it is understood that the earlier Indian writers reflected the idea of women’s rights and liberty indirectly, without branding themselves as feminist writers. Whereas after 70’s women writers, who are activists themselves involved in creating feminist literature to popularize the philosophy of feminism and bring awareness about the equal rights for women – socially, politically and economically. They further focused on the individualism and sexuality issues of women in their works. Literature is said to be a vehicle for social transformation. The feminist literature also can be said to have achieved its target of bringing change in the society to considerable extent.

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